

Defense Strategies for Adversarial Machine Learning: A Survey

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Abstract

Adversarial Machine Learning (AML) is a recently introduced technique, aiming to deceive Machine Learning (ML) models by providing falsified inputs to render those models ineffective. Consequently, most researchers focus on detecting new AML attacks that can undermine existing ML infrastructures, overlooking at the same time the significance of defense strategies. This article constitutes a survey of the existing literature on AML attacks and defenses with a special focus on a taxonomy of recent works on AML defense techniques for different application domains, such as audio, cyber-security, NLP, and computer vision. The proposed survey also explores the methodology of the defense solutions and compares them using several criteria, such as whether they are attack- and/or domain-agnostic, deploy appropriate AML evaluation metrics, and whether they share their source code and/or their evaluation datasets. To the best of our knowledge, this article constitutes the first survey that seeks to systematize the existing knowledge focusing solely on the defense solutions against AML and providing innovative directions for future research on tackling the increasing threat of AML.

Keywords: Survey, Machine Learning, Adversarial Machine Learning, Defense Methods, Computer Vision, Cybersecurity, Natural Language Processing, Audio

1. Introduction

The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) principles and mechanisms led to the revolution of various technological domains by introducing automation and self-managed operation for society, including novel advances such as smart cities, self-driving cars, autonomous ships, 5G/6G networks as well as Industry 4.0 systems. However, the utilization of AI almost in every aspect of society's daily activities has introduced a new and enormous attack surface that targets Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms compromising their functionality and affecting their performance, which are termed in literature as Adversarial Machine Learning (AML) [1]. Considering the heavy applicability of ML and DL also in critical tasks (e.g., cancer diagnosis) [2], AML can lead to severe consequences, varying from data privacy leakage to even loss of life.

Even though AI is heavily applied to critical tasks, the security of AI systems takes a back seat when developing and evaluating ML/DL models. These models are usually developed based on the assumption that both the datasets used for training are trustworthy and the evaluating environment is secure. Hence, most AI systems are vulnerable to various attacks that aim to impact the algorithms' decisions by modifying the training data (known as poisoning attacks [3]) or altering the output of the model (known as evasion attacks [4]). Current

research delves into attacking ML/DL models rather than defending them. More specifically, existing works mainly focus on the computer vision domain by introducing various methods for the generation of adversarial samples, which, when injected in the testing phase, can reduce the algorithms' performance significantly [5]. Nevertheless, novel AML attacks have been recently expanded also in other domains, including health, audio, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and cybersecurity, as well as in various algorithms (e.g., Convolutional Neural Networks, Random Forest, and Support Vector Machines), indicating the severity of AML [6, 7].

The major part of current surveys in the field of AML focuses only on a specific domain (e.g., computer vision or cybersecurity) and elaborates on the attacks against AI systems without delving into the possible defenses. In addition, several articles in the literature highlight that the research on the defense solutions against AML attacks is still in its infancy and further research should be conducted to tackle the growth of AML attacks [8, 9, 10]. Additionally, to the best of our knowledge, the existing AML survey articles do not focus on the existing defense methods to counter AML attacks, leaving a knowledge gap for researchers aiming at the development of new detection and mitigation methods.

To this end, this article introduces a domain-agnostic and large-scale survey of the defense methods designed to tackle AML attacks. Specifically, it aims to organize the existing knowledge and provide directions for future research to facilitate the scientific community toward proposing more efficient and robust defense solutions to address the ongoing threat of AML. Thus, the methodological steps depicted in Figure 1 have been followed. More specifically, in *Step 1*, the existing literature

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Figure 1: Methodological Steps

was collected utilizing a systematic methodology discussed in Section 2.1. In *Step 2*, the current surveys in AML field were studied, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses as well as their directions for future research, where almost all the surveys identified that further research is needed to minimize the threat of AML. Later, the existing defenses aiming to tackle AML were examined to identify common methods and traits based on which they will be categorized. In *Step 3*, a taxonomy of the existing defenses that aim to counter AML attacks was created. To the best of our knowledge, this article constitutes the first attempt to introduce a domain-agnostic taxonomy of AML defenses. This allows to systematize of the existing knowledge and extract insights about the current AML defense state using a comparison against several criteria, such as whether the defenses are attack and/or domain-agnostic, their application domain, and their defense category (see Section 6). The taxonomy is domain-agnostic since, instead of focusing on the defense methods of a particular domain, four different domains (cybersecurity, computer vision, NLP, and audio) have been considered. The selection of these domains was performed based on the prominence of AML attacks against them [11]. In *Step 4*, the evaluation datasets and metrics were identified based on the existing literature in order to present the datasets and metrics that already exist and can be deployed for validating AML defense solutions. Finally, in *Step 5*, relying on the knowledge obtained from the taxonomy, numerous directions for future research were proposed.

The novelty of this work mainly focuses on studying the available defense solutions of the literature that aim to tackle AML attacks and put them under a common taxonomy based on their primary traits, regardless of their application domain. Please note that some of the presented categories of the taxonomy (e.g., adversarial training, feature reduction) have been presented in previous works that emphasize more on AML attacks than on the defenses against AML attacks [5, 8]; however, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt for creating a domain-agnostic taxonomy of AML defenses contributing on enhancing the efforts on tackling AML attacks. Moreover, another novelty of this work is that based on the analysis of the existing defenses and the taxonomy, several gaps have been identified in the literature which translated into directions for future research (see Section 6).

Concretely, the article builds upon the following contributions:

- A domain-agnostic survey on the defense strategies against AML attacks is conducted, including both mitigation and detection methods.
- The defense methods against AML attacks that are present in literature are presented in terms of a taxonomy, focusing on different domains, such as cybersecurity, computer vision, NLP, and audio.
- The currently faced issues and challenges for the protection of ML/DL systems against AML attacks are thor-

oughly discussed, including mitigation methods such as adversarial training, defense distillation, ensemble methods, and defense methods as distance-based, feature squeezing, statistical.

- Innovative research directions for building a research framework on AML defense strategies based on existing AML datasets and evaluation metrics on the effectiveness of detection methods against AML attacks are illustrated.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology followed to collect the surveyed papers and presents the existing surveys in the AML field. Section 3 delves into the AML attacks. Section 4 introduces a taxonomy of the existing defenses against AML attacks. Section 5 gathers the existing AML evaluation metrics and datasets, while Section 6 elaborates on the findings of the proposed work and provides directions for future research. Finally, Section 7 outlines the critical points of the proposed survey.

2. Literature Collection and Related Work

This section elaborates on the systematic methodology that was followed to collect the existing works that were discussed in this survey as well as presents the existing surveys in the AML domain along with the limitations of the literature that this work aims to address.

2.1. Literature Collection

Threat to validity: A systematic methodology was followed in order for this survey to detect and collect related research papers and surveys that tackle AML attacks as well as defenses [12, 13]. In particular, the following academic platforms: Google Scholar¹, ACM Digital Library², IEEE Xplore³, ScienceDirect⁴, SpringerLink⁵, arXiv⁶, and Nicholas Carlini website⁷ were scrutinized. In more detail, to collect the research papers for this study, the following queries were deployed: (i) adversarial machine learning defense, (ii) adversarial machine learning mitigation, (iii) adversarial training, (iv) adversarial machine learning survey, (v) defense against black-box attacks, (vi) defense against gray-box attacks, (vii) defense against white-box attacks, (viii) defense against poisoning attacks, and (ix) defense against evasion attacks as well as three selection criteria: (1) the subject of the paper aligns with the topic of the proposed survey; (2) the article was published after 2014; (3) the article is applied to one of the following domains: computer vision, cybersecurity, NLP, and audio. Please note that even using nine different queries some relevant papers might have been missed

¹<https://scholar.google.com>

²<https://dl.acm.org/>

³<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>

⁴<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

⁵<https://link.springer.com/>

⁶<https://arxiv.org/>

⁷<https://nicholas.carlini.com/writing/2019/all-adversarial-example-papers.html>

Table 1: Allocation of the surveyed papers per year

Year	# Papers	Year	# Papers	Year	# Papers
2014	1	2017	6	2020	14
2015	2	2018	6	2021	15
2016	1	2019	8	2022	8

Table 2: Allocation of the surveyed papers per domain

Domain	# Papers
Computer Vision	22
Cybersecurity	22
NLP	7
Audio	13

since authors often deploy a different terminology that is not commonly used [14].

Based on the selected criteria, 68 articles were selected from which seven are existing surveys in AML field that mainly focus on the attacks and not the defenses (see Section 2.2), and 61 are proposing a defense method against one or more AML attacks in the fields of computer vision, cybersecurity, NLP, and audio classification. The selected papers were published between 2014 and 2022. More specifically, the allocation of the number of surveyed papers per year and domain is depicted in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. To enhance the comprehension of the tables, it shall be noted that some defenses have been evaluated on several domains (e.g., image and audio classification), hence in Table 2, some papers are categorized in more than one domain.

2.2. Related Work

Currently, only a handful of surveys have been published that mostly concentrate on examining the features of AML attacks and their applicability to different domains. This section elaborates on previous surveys in the AML domain. More precisely, the strengths and weaknesses of each work were discussed, and the identified gaps in the literature were highlighted.

Wang et al. [8] presented a survey regarding the security of ML/DL models under adversarial settings. The authors provided background information about the field of ML, the treated model, and the attack surface. Nevertheless, this research’s backbone was the analysis of AML attacks and their possible defense strategies. The survey concluded that future work on ML security should pay more attention to the defense strategies of DL techniques, data privacy, and the security evaluation of ML/DL methods. One major limitation of this work is that the authors mainly focused on AML attacks in the computer vision domain. Notably, they elaborated on common AML attacks (e.g., L-BFGS, FGSM, and C&W) that applied to image classification or visual recognition.

Qiu et al. [9] reviewed the literature on the AML attack field, performing a thorough analysis of its characteristics. The authors also discussed the application of the various AML attacks on different domains, such as Computer Vision, NLP, and Cyberspace Security, as well as in the physical world. Further, the paper shortly presented some research focusing on the mitigation of common AML attacks and stressed that defenses are mainly focused on a particular adversarial attack type as well as that none of the current defense methods aiming at tackling multiple AML attacks.

Pitropakis et al. [10] performed a thorough taxonomy of the AML attacks features. The authors broke down the key

features of the attacks and categorized them based on the application of ML that compromises such as intrusion detection, spam filtering, visual recognition, other applications, and multipurpose. This survey discusses various attack types on the domains mentioned above and it considers the ML algorithms that each attack targets. Also, the authors provided useful statistics about the distribution of the investigated papers regarding the attackers’ knowledge (e.g., 64% focused on *white-box* attacks, 56% focused on *black-box* attacks), the AML attack type (e.g., 52% related with evasion attacks and 56% with poisoning attacks), the targeted domain (e.g., 88% dealt with classification tasks and 17% dealt with clustering). Finally, the paper highlighted that future research should focus on creating immunity to perturbations, multiple adversaries, randomized adversarial approaches, and digital forensics for AML.

Martins et al. [15] explored the application of AML attacks on intrusion and malware detection fields. The authors surveyed works that employed AML methods, such as FGSM, JSMA, C&W, and GAN, to attack ML-based IDS and malware detectors. The paper also presented some general defense strategies for AML attacks but it did not elaborate on them. Towards the same direction, Rosenberg et al. [16] discussed the risk posed by AML attacks in the cybersecurity domain and presented state-of-the-art AML research papers focused on cybersecurity. The authors highlighted the differences between the AML attacks in the computer vision and cybersecurity domains, concluding that it is more difficult to perform an AML attack on malware or intrusion detection ML models. Moreover, the paper covered several AML attacks in the cybersecurity domain, analyzing multiple fields such as malware detection, malicious URL detection, network intrusion detection, spam filtering, Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), Industrial Control Systems (ICS), as well as biometric systems. The authors emphasized that only a limited number of defense methods have been proposed to tackle AML attacks or develop more robust solutions in the cybersecurity domain.

Qayyum et al. [17] discussed the challenges aroused by AML in the Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAV) domain. The authors elaborated on the ML pipeline deployed in CAV, the existing AML attacks on CAV, and methods to increase the robustness of the ML models. Moreover, the authors also mentioned open research issues and provided future directions to raise awareness among the readers toward the development and application of robust and effective ML models in CAV. Even though this work gives readers a comprehensive view of AML attacks and defenses, it is limited to their application in CAV.

Bai et al. [18] presented a taxonomy of adversarial training

methods in the computer vision domain. The taxonomy classifies previous works on Adversarial Regularization, Curriculum-based Adversarial Training, Ensemble Adversarial Training, Adversarial Training with Adaptive ϵ , Adversarial Training with Semi-supervised/Unsupervised Learning, efficient Adversarial Training, and other variants. This survey provides a comprehensive view of works on the adversarial training domain; however, it only focuses on the computer vision domain without elaborating on the pros and cons of each work.

A recent survey with the same grounds as the proposed paper was presented by Machado et al. [19]. The authors reviewed the latest studies on AML attacks that target image classification tasks from the defender’s perspective. This work, except for studying AML attacks on the Computer Vision domain, elaborates on a taxonomy of defenses against adversarial images. The AML attacks on the Computer Vision domain mainly target DL models (e.g., CNN, DNN); hence the authors did not elaborate on attacks against ML models. Furthermore, the authors discussed possible reasons for the existence of adversarial examples and presented directions for future works. Finally, this work highlights the importance of extensive and up-to-date review papers in AML to direct researchers toward tackling this ongoing threat and protecting ML/DL models. To the best of our knowledge, this is the only article that thoroughly analyzes and categorizes the defense solutions against AML attacks; nevertheless, it is limited to the Computer Vision domain and DL models.

Table 3 summarizes the existing surveys in terms of general features, such as the application domain as well as whether they present also the defenses, discuss adversarial example generation methods, provide insights about the evaluation (e.g., metrics to evaluate the attack performance or robustness), and focus on the attack surface.

To sum up, almost all the surveys [10, 15, 16, 17, 19] emphasize the fact that future works in the AML domain should focus on developing defense methods to tackle the expansion of AML attacks. However, there is a clear gap in the literature regarding the surveys that elaborate exclusively on the existing defense solutions, since all the surveys in the AML domain delve into various types of AML attacks dealing with the problem of AML attacks from the attackers’ perspective [10, 17]. Some of the existing surveys briefly discussed a few defense solutions, but their efforts were focusing on a particular domain (e.g., Martins et al. [15] presented a limited number of defense methods to tackle AML attacks in the fields of intrusion and malware detection). Overall, existing surveys in the area often neglect to investigate the defense solutions in a domain-agnostic manner (e.g., studying the defenses against AML attacks regardless of their application domain). Based on this observation, this article focuses exclusively on the available defenses against AML attacks. To this end, it studies the available defenses of the literature in various domains (as explained in Section 2.1) to provide a thorough taxonomy and systematize the existing knowledge in order to facilitate researchers in developing new defense methods and building robust ML/DL models. Towards this direction, this paper also presents insights into the evaluation of AML defense methods. More specifi-

Table 3: Summarizing existing surveys

Paper/Year	Domain	Defense	Adversarial Examples	Evaluation	Attack Surface
Wang et al. (2019) [8]	Computer Vision	✓	✓	✓	✓
Qu et al. (2019) [9]	Multi-domain	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pitropakis et al. (2019) [10]	Multi-domain	✗	✗	✗	✗
Martins et al. (2020) [15]	Intrusion & malware	✓	✓	✓	✓
Qayyum et al. (2020) [17]	CAV	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bai et al. (2021) [18]	Computer Vision	✓	✗	✓	✓
Machado et al. (2021) [19]	Image Classification	✓	✓	✓	✓
Rosenberg et al. (2021) [16]	Cybersecurity	✓	✓	✗	✓

cally, the publicly available AML datasets are discussed along with evaluation metrics appropriate for testing the robustness of ML and DL models as well as the efficacy of defense methods against AML attacks.

3. Adversarial Machine Learning Attacks

The AML attacks have been thoroughly discussed in previous literature works [8, 10, 16]. Thus, this article does not focus on introducing the numerous attacks that are available in the literature. Instead, in this section fundamental information about AML attacks is analyzed, which is essential for the reader to grasp the proposed concept. Figure 2 presents an overview of AML attacks against ML/DL models. The rest of the section presents the adversary’s knowledge, capability, and possible attack types for AML attacks.

Figure 2: Adversary attacking AI models

3.1. Adversary’s Knowledge

An essential factor of an AML attack is the knowledge that the adversary has about the target model. Based on the amount of the adversary’s knowledge and, as an extension, the access she has to the model, AML attacks can be classified into three categories: *white-box*, *black-box*, and *gray-box*.

White-box. In white-box attacks, the adversary has complete knowledge of the system, the algorithm’s architecture, hyper-parameters, and training data. While the amount of knowledge that white-box attacks require is rarely available in real-life scenarios, it is not unrealistic to occur. This knowledge can be acquired either by reverse engineering the model or by an insider.

For example, via reverse engineering, adversaries might recover the model’s components (e.g., architecture, hyperparameters) and gain white-box access. As one can understand, white-box attacks are the most potent type of AML attacks; thus, they are usually deployed to evaluate the robustness of ML/DL models and defenses. Namely, if a model is robust against white-box attacks, it will also be robust against gray-box and black-box attacks.

Black-box. In a black-box attack, the adversary has no knowledge of the system or the deployed defenses. The only information the adversary has is that, given the input, she can monitor the outcome of the system. Nevertheless, in some cases, the number of queries she can perform is limited (e.g., it might arouse suspicion), which hardens her work. Szegedy et al. [20] was the first that observed the *adversarial example transferability*, namely adversarial examples created to be misclassified by a model are possible to be also misclassified by a different model, even when the models are trained on different datasets. Papernot et al. [21] carried out black-box attacks on a Deep Neural Network (DNN), based on the adversarial example transferability effect. The authors conducted the attacks by only observing the outputs of the DNN given particular inputs. Their attack strategy included a substitute model, which was trained using synthetic inputs labeled by the DNN model to craft adversarial examples that were used to attack the DNN model.

Gray-box. The gray-box attack refers to the attack paradigm, where the adversary has some degree of knowledge about the system or the deployed defenses. In real-life scenarios, commonly, the adversary cannot obtain white-box access; however, it may receive partial pieces of information, such as some of the classifier’s features, the class label, or in the case of DNN, the results of the hidden layers.

3.2. Adversary’s Capability

An adversary’s capabilities can be grouped into two categories: *attack influence* and *data manipulation*. The attack influence can be further divided into *causative attacks* that happen when the adversary modifies the training data (e.g., in case a system is retrained) or *exploratory attacks* that occur when the adversary skews the data during the testing phase. On the other hand, data manipulation is the process that defines how the samples or features can be modified. For instance, it determines which features can be altered without compromising the scope of the original sample.

3.3. Attack Types

According to previous works [9, 10], there are two major types of attacks that an adversary can perform on ML/DL models: *poisoning attacks* and *evasion attacks*. Both attacks aim to maximize the generalization error of the decision-making process to affect the system’s decision.

3.3.1. Poisoning Attacks

The poisoning attack is the attack type that targets the system’s learning process during the training phase. The poisoning attacks can be further classified into three categories.

Training Data Modification was the first type of poisoning attack proposed in the literature. The modification of training data includes modifying or deleting training data or injecting adversarial examples on the training dataset [3].

Label Manipulation or Label Flipping occurs when the adversary alters the labels of the training samples. Hence, this method is only applicable to supervised learning tasks. Biggio et al. [22] presented that randomly flipping 40% of the training labels can significantly reduce the performance of SVM classifiers.

Input Feature Manipulation is similar to label manipulation attacks; however, instead of altering the labels, the adversary can manipulate the training samples’ features parsed by the ML/DL algorithm [23].

3.3.2. Evasion Attacks

An evasion attack targets the testing phase of already trained ML/DL classifiers by manipulating the samples without having access to the training data aiming at violating the system’s integrity [4]. Since these attacks are performed in the testing phase, they are the most practical attack types and are widely used. For instance, the injection of adversarial examples during the testing phase to affect the prediction performance of a classifier is considered an evasion attack. A typical evasion attack is an input/output black-box attack, where the adversary inserts arbitrary inputs on an ML/DL model to observe its output [24]. The attacker’s objective hence violates the integrity of the system, either by conducting a targeted or an indiscriminate attack, depending on whether she is targeting a particular system or not.

3.4. Adversarial Example Generation Methods

This section presents the most known adversarial example generation methods in the literature. These methods were initially developed to be applied in the computer vision domain (e.g., to attack image classifiers); however, in the last couple of years they have been also implemented in other domains, such as intrusion detection [25], environmental sound classification [26], and question answering [27].

Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM). Goodfellow et al. [28] introduced the FGSM method that computes the gradient of the cost function based on the model’s input. More specifically, FGSM generates adversarial examples that are the original samples with a small perturbation (i.e., modification) to affect the prediction of the model (i.e., classifier). The adversarial examples are generated by Equation 1:

$$X^* = X + \epsilon \text{sign}(\nabla_x J(\theta, X, y)), \quad (1)$$

where X^* is the adversarial example, ϵ indicates the value that controls the magnitude of the perturbation (i.e., the noise that

will be applied), J represents the cost function of the model, ∇_x is the gradient of the model based on the sample X and its label y , and θ is the model’s hyper-parameters.

FGSM, except for its application in the image classification field, has also been employed in other fields, for instance, cybersecurity [29, 30]. However, as mentioned by Rosenberg et al. [16], the application of FGSM in the cybersecurity domain is more challenging than in computer vision due to the nature of the samples.

Jacobian based Saliency Map Attack (JSMA). Papernot et al. [31] presented the JSMA method that produces adversarial examples using saliency maps and employs the Jacobian matrix of the model to calculate the sensitivity direction. The Jacobian matrix of a model F with respect to the input samples X is calculated via the equation 2:

$$J_F = \frac{\delta F(X)}{\delta X} \quad (2)$$

Later, J_F is deployed to generate *adversarial saliency maps* used to identify the features of the input data most relevant to the model’s decision. Namely, the features that should be perturbed to affect the model’s classification. Finally, the JSMA method checks whether the alterations have affected the model to misclassify the input. If they have not affected it, another set of features is selected, and the process repeats until an adversarial saliency map arises that can be utilized to generate an adversarial example.

Limited-memory Broyden Fletcher Goldfarb Shanno (L-BFGS). Szegedy et al. [20] was one of the first who observed that adding perturbations to images can deceive DL models and lead to misclassifications. Notably, the authors generate adversarial examples by adding perturbations to an image having as a scope to reduce the added perturbation r under L_2 distance:

$$\min \|r\|_2^2, f(x+r) = y, \quad (3)$$

where r is the perturbation, f is the loss function of the model, x is the original image, and y is the incorrect prediction label. Because Equation 3 is non-trivial, the authors deployed a box-constrained L-BFGS to solve it. A drawback of the L-BFGS method is that even though it is efficient at generating adversarial examples, it is computationally ineffective.

DeepFool. Moosavi et al. [32] proposed a repetitive procedure for creating adversarial examples. This method minimizes the Euclidean distance between the adversarial and original samples. DeepFool is comprised of the calculation of a linear decision limit, which divides the samples that belong to different classes. In DNN, it is challenging to find linear decision limits; hence the perturbations are added repetitively by applying this method multiple times. The robustness of a classifier is calculated by Equation 4.

$$\Delta(x, F) = \min_r \|r\|_2, F(x+r) \neq F(x), \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta(x, F)$ is the robustness of classifier F given a sample x and r is the minimal perturbation that it can alter the esti-

mated label $F(x)$. DeepFool is a powerful method for generating adversarial examples with fewer perturbations than FGSM and JSMA; however, it is computationally expensive.

Carlini & Wagner (C&W). Carlini & Wagner introduced an effective adversarial example generation method that identifies the less possible perturbations based on a distance metric (L_0, L_2, L_∞). The L_0 and L_2 concluded to have much fewer perturbations than SOTA (FGSM and JSMA). The aim of C&W is to minimize $D(x, x + \delta)$ such that $C(x + \delta) = t, x + \delta \in [0, 1]^n$, where (x) is the sample, δ is the perturbation, and Δ is the distance metric. Namely, the goal is to find a small alteration δ to make on the sample that will change its classification without ruining its type (e.g., if the sample is an image and a perturbation δ is added, then the result should be still a valid image).

Basic Interaction Method (BIM). Kurakin et al. [33] proposed an adversarial example generation method based on FGSM. More specifically, BIM is an extension of FGSM, meaning that it adopts an iteration process to perturbate the pixels of an image, ensuring that the values are pruned within a certain margin of the source image. Even though BIM has been originally tested in the image classification domain, it has also been applied in the IoT domain [34] and intrusion detection [35].

At this point, it should be noted that there are also other methods for adversarial example generation in the literature, such as Projected Gradient Descent (PGD), Bit Coordinate Ascent (BCA), and Bit Gradient Ascent (BGA). However, this paper does not elaborate on them mainly for two reasons. First, they are not widely used, i.e., they have been deployed by a few previous works. Second, they are based on other adversarial example generation methods (e.g., PGD is based on FGSM).

4. Adversarial Machine Learning Defenses

The rise of AML attacks has inspired the scientific community to drive more research on designing and developing novel defense methods against such attacks. This section elaborates on a taxonomy of AML defense methods, which to the best of our knowledge, is the first large-scale taxonomy of the available defenses against AML attacks. As it is shown in Figure 3, the taxonomy includes two main axes based on the defense objective: (i) Mitigation and (ii) Detection, also included in the following part of this section in 4.1 and 4.2 respectively. Finally, the taxonomy analyzes various types of defenses against AML attacks on four pioneer domains that gather the most works of the literature (i.e., cybersecurity, computer vision, NLP, and audio). Figure 3 provides an overview of the AML defense methods that are present in literature.

4.1. Mitigation

The mitigation category refers to proactive defenses that strive to enhance the robustness of ML/DL models against AML attacks. The available mitigation methods are presented below.

Figure 3: Taxonomy of AML defense methods

4.1.1. Adversarial Training

The adversarial training defense method aims to enhance the model’s robustness by utilizing a training dataset that contains both benign and adversarial examples. The difference between traditional and adversarial training is shown in Figure 4, where in adversarial training both original and perturbed data are deployed in the learning phase.

Figure 4: Traditional VS adversarial training

Specifically, given a training dataset D that contains the tuple $X = (x, y)$ (where x is the sample and y is the label), an adversarial sample x^* is crafted by an algorithm A based on x and forms a new tuple X^* that has the same label (y) as X , namely $X^* = (x^*, y)$. Later, the training dataset D will be expanded with X^* resulting in $T = \{X, X^*\}$. The ML/DL algorithm is then re-trained using the expanded dataset, which will result in a more robust model in theory.

Adversarial training is the literature’s most well-known defense method against AML attacks. To this end, most of the existing defenses are based on different variations of adversarial training. It should be noted that because the majority of defenses are based on adversarial training, this section categorizes the defenses of this category based on their application domain.

COMPUTER VISION

Adversarial training was first introduced in the computer vision domain [28]; hence it has received considerable attention

from the research community during these years. Goodfellow et al. [28] were among the first that raised the adversarial training defense in the computer vision field. The authors deploy the FGSM method to generate adversarial examples and, via adversarial training, managed to decrease the error rate of a DNN image classifier from 89.4% to 17.9%. The experiments were performed on the MNIST dataset⁸.

Huang et al. [36] studied the role of adversarial training on classifiers’ robustness and proposed a new approach to generate adversarial examples. The authors employed a min-max adversarial training approach, i.e., Learning With an Adversary (LWA), to train a DNN image classifier. The experimental results indicate that LWA accomplishes better robustness and high accuracy on original samples compared to existing methods (e.g., [28]) on both MNIST and CIFAR-10⁹ datasets.

Madry et al. [37] deployed PGD and FGSM methods to generate adversarial examples, which were used to retrain a DNN. The authors deployed black-box and white-box adversary’s knowledge and proved that the proposed adversarial training approach could achieve robustness against different attacks. Notably, the DNN trained with the MNIST dataset accomplished 89% accuracy on the strongest AML attack (white-box & PGD), while on the same attack, the DNN trained with CIFAR-10 dataset achieved 46%. The drawback of the proposed defense is that it is computationally complex; thus, it is difficult to test it on large datasets.

Sankaranarayanan et al. [38] proposed a new regularization approach for DNN image classifiers that improves the adversarial robustness in comparison with traditional adversarial training methods. More specifically, the authors compared the proposed layer-wise adversarial training with FGSM and FGSM-inter (i.e., a variation of FGSM where intermediate layer activations are perturbed). They concluded that when perturbing intermediate layers and not only the input layer of a DNN, the classification performance is improved. However, when perturbing only the input layer the adversarial robustness is improved. Thus, there is a trade-off between the adversarial robustness and the regularization effect on original data.

The authors of [39] proposed an adversarial training algorithm that eliminates the additional time that emerges from the generation of adversarial examples. The algorithm eliminates this overhead by recycling the gradient information computed when updating the model’s parameters. The proposed algorithm needs almost the same training time as in original training to produce robust DNN models, and it is 3 – 30 times faster than previous works (e.g., [37]). The experimental results concluded that the produced models accomplish slightly better accuracy on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets than conventional adversarial training methods. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm can also be applied on large-scale datasets, like ImageNet¹⁰ attaining 40% accuracy against PGD attacks.

Xie et al. [40] combined feature denoising with adversarial training to enhance CNNs’ adversarial robustness. The pro-

⁸<http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist/>

⁹<https://www.cs.toronto.edu/kriz/cifar.html>

¹⁰<https://www.image-net.org/>

posed method improves the adversarial robustness in white-box and black-box adversarial knowledge against PGD AML attacks. More specifically, the authors deployed the large ImageNet dataset, and in a 10-iteration PGD white-box attack, the proposed method achieved 55.7% accuracy (the prior state-of-the-art has 27.9% accuracy). Moreover, in the extreme case of 2000-iterations PGD white-box attacks, the proposed method attained 42.6% accuracy, while in a black-box setting against 48 unknown attackers, the proposed method achieved 50.6% accuracy, and it was ranked first in Competition on Adversarial Attacks and Defenses 2018.

The authors of [41] introduced the concept of combining ensemble learning with adversarial training. Their approach merges the training data with adversarial perturbations generated from three different AML attacks instead of one. Specifically, the authors deployed the FGSM, the Single-step Least-Likely Class Method (Step-LL), and the iterative I-FGSM. The experiments were performed using several variations of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Fully Connected Network (FCN) models on the ImageNet dataset with white-box and black-box adversary’s knowledge. The results indicate that ensemble adversarial training is not robust against white-box I-FGSM and Step-LL, while it enhances the models’ robustness against black-box attacks.

Lal et al. [42] proposed a robust image classification framework for detecting Diabetic Retinopathy. The authors employed a CNN model (Darknet53) to perform the classification and deployed an adversarial training approach to enhance the model’s robustness against AML attacks. The FGSM, DeepFool, and Speckle Noise AML attacks have been used to evaluate their framework. Four different adversarial training methods were employed, and the best robustness was accomplished by mixed adversarial training (MAT) in which the training dataset included adversarial examples from all the AML attacks. To be more precise, MAT achieved 92% correct label prediction.

Ding et al. [43] developed a method for restoring images from degradation focusing on visual context prediction in the case of autonomous vehicles. The proposed method is based on a multi-stage conditional Generative Adversarial Network (cGAN) for image restoration that employs adversarial training to detect images from various types of degradation. The authors performed the adversarial training using both original and degraded images using various degradation methods, such as motion blurring, Gaussian filtering, average filtering, Gaussian noising, oversharpening, and JPEG compression. The evaluation results concluded that the proposed method is more efficient for image restoration than the existing works and other methods (CycleGAN, DeblurGAN).

Xu et al. [44] proposed a Fair-Robust-Learning (FRL) framework to mitigate the disparity of accuracy and robustness between different classes introduced by adversarial training. The authors increased the perturbation margin ϵ during training in the generation of adversarial examples process for a specific class. This way, the class’s robustness is improved, and the boundary error is reduced. The FRL framework employed a

DNN model and was evaluated using the CIFAR-10 and SVHN¹¹ datasets. Moreover, FRL improved the lower robust error of [37] and [45] by 10% – 15%.

CYBERSECURITY

Khamis et al. [29] proposed one of the first adversarial training approaches in the cybersecurity domain. Their approach was based on the min-max formulation aiming to enhance the robustness of ML/DL-based IDSs. The authors developed several ML and DL classifiers, such as DNN, RF, AdaBoost (AB), Naive Bayes (NB), and Support Vector Machine (SVM), which were trained on the UNSW-NB15¹² dataset. Four AML attacks were investigated (dFGSM, rFGSM, BCA, and BGA) in white-box adversary’s knowledge that was performed in the DNN. In the baseline model, the dFGSM attack reached the higher evasion rate (100%), rFGSM and BGA yielded 99%, while BCA attained 64.4%. Using min-max adversarial training, the experimental results show that the evasion rate was significantly reduced. Moreover, the authors also concluded that the PCA feature selection method enhances the model’s robustness against AML attacks.

An extension of the previous work was proposed in [46], where the authors deployed three different DNN DL-based IDS on Artificial Neural Network (ANN), CNN, and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The IDSes were trained to detect malicious network traffic on two well-known datasets (UNSW-NB15 and NSL-KDD¹³). Using white-box adversary’s knowledge, the authors performed five AML attacks (FGSM, BIM, PGD, C&W, and DeepFool). The AML attacks were highly effective since the accuracy of the IDSes decreased from approximately 20% to 90% (C&W AML attack against RNN on the NSL-KDD dataset). However, in many cases, the adversarial training-based min-max formulation managed to reach the baseline results of the DL-based IDSes showing that it could be considered a reliable defense method. Furthermore, the authors highlight that C&W and DeepFool AML attacks on RNN are the most difficult to tackle.

Fu et al. [47] studied the robustness of three DL-based IDS against AML attacks. Particularly, the authors utilized the FGSM method to generate adversarial examples to evaluate the robustness of the CNN, LSTM, and GRU models. The models were trained with three different methods (normal training, adversarial training, and adversarial re-training). The experiments were performed on the CSE-CIC-IDS 2018 dataset¹⁴. After the FGSM attack, the models’ accuracy decreased by 20-40%, while the least affected model was the CNN. After the adversarial training and adversarial re-training, the models’ robustness increased significantly. However, a drawback of this work is that the performance against the original samples was decreased compared to the results when trained only with the original samples. Another work along the same line is proposed in [48],

¹¹<http://ufldl.stanford.edu/housenumbers/>

¹²<https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/unswnb15-dataset>

¹³<http://www.di.uniba.it/~andresini/datasets.html>

¹⁴<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2018.html>

where the authors also deployed min-max adversarial training. In this work, only a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) classifier was evaluated using three AML attacks, named FGSM, PGD-K L_2 , and PGD-K L_∞ , without discussing the adversary's knowledge. The authors concluded that PGD with a larger K value (e.g., PGD-40 min-max training) offers increased robustness.

Apruzee et al. [49] presented a Deep Reinforcement Learning to automatically generate adversarial examples in the form of network flows against botnet detectors. The adversarial examples were generated by altering a few essential traffic flow features (e.g., duration, sent bytes, received bytes, and transmitted packets). The generated adversarial examples were deployed to create an augmented dataset that, via adversarial training, can enhance the resilience of botnet detectors. The authors utilized two datasets in their experiments, CTU and Botnet, and two ML botnet detectors based on RF and Wide and Deep Learning (WnD)¹⁵. The evaluation results concluded that the hardened botnet detectors increased the detection rate from 0.58 to 0.88 against the adversarial examples without affecting the performance when tested with non-adversarial examples.

Towards the same direction, Anthi et al. [25] utilized adversarial training to improve the robustness of two classifiers (J48 decision tree and RF) designed to detect attacks on ICS. The authors performed a data poisoning attack based on the gray-box adversary's knowledge; they only had access to the dataset and the features, while they had not any other knowledge about the model. The adversarial examples that were utilized to perform the AML attack were generated using the JSMA method, and the detection performance of RF and J48 models decreased by 6% and 11%, respectively. As a countermeasure to this data poisoning attack, the authors employed the adversarial training method using 10% of the adversarial examples to retrain the classifiers. Afterward, the RF and J48 models were applied to the unknown adversarial examples, where they accomplished 11% and 17% higher F1-scores respectively.

Vitorino et al. [50] introduced the Adaptive Perturbation Pattern Method (A2PM) to generate realistic adversarial examples. The authors showcased their method on two scenarios (i.e., Enterprise and IoT in a gray-box attack setting) using the MLP and RF models, where they only had knowledge about the features. The adversarial examples significantly lowered the performance of MLP and RF in both scenarios. Furthermore, the authors evaluated the models also using adversarial training and concluded that when the models are adversarially trained their robustness against adversarial examples is significantly improved.

Debicha et al. [35] studied the effect of adversarial training in a DL-based IDS. More specifically, the authors performed white-box AML attacks using the FGSM, BIM, and PGD methods. The experiments were performed on the NSL-KDD dataset, where the baseline model reached 99.61% detection accuracy. The FGSM attack decreased the accuracy to 14.13%, while BIM and PGD reduced it even more to 8.85%. After the adversarial training using the PGD adversarial examples, the model's

robustness increased significantly (it is not mentioned exactly how much); nevertheless, the authors highlighted that there is a trade-off of slightly decreasing the detection accuracy on clean data, namely when there are no adversarial examples. In addition, the authors concluded that increasing the percentage of adversarial examples in the training phase does not necessarily enhance the model's robustness.

Rashid et al. [34] investigated the effects of AML attacks on ML/DL-based IDSs designed to detect attacks against IoT smart city applications and proposed a defense method based on adversarial training to enhance the models' robustness. The authors utilized three classifiers (MLP, DT, and RF) and trained them using the DS2OS dataset¹⁶. Moreover, they evaluated the five most known AML attacks (JSMA, FGSM, BIM, DeepFool, and C&W); however, it is not mentioned what the adversary's knowledge is (e.g., white-box, black-box, etc.). All the AML attacks significantly decreased the performance of the models varying from 36% to 78%; however, the JSMA and C&W attacks were the most successful. The authors concluded that the MLP shows relatively higher robustness than the other shallow ML classifiers. For the adversarial training, the authors deployed the adversarial examples that were generated by the C&W method, where 60% of the samples were added to the training set, and the remaining 40% was included in the testing set. The authors concluded that the adversarial training is sufficient to maintain the classifier's performance against adversarial AML attacks. The baseline classifiers MLP, DT, and RF accomplished 99.43%, 99.35%, and 99.41% accuracy, while the re-trained classifiers achieved 99.20%, 99.19%, and 99.19%, respectively.

NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

In the NLP domain, there are several works in the literature, such as [51, 52, 53, 54] that deploy adversarial training as a mean to improve the prediction performance of NLP models rather than enhancing their robustness against AML attacks. Furthermore, other works that aim to enhance the NLP model's robustness are usually focused on BERT NLP models [55]. Subsequently, the following part will focus on the adversarial training methods that aim to mitigate AML attacks in the NLP domain.

Liu et al. [56] presented a comprehensive study on adversarial pre-training aiming to enhance both the generalization and robustness of NLP models even though prior works treat them as inversely related terms. The authors proposed an algorithm, which combines the training process with applying perturbations in the embedding space. The algorithms were applied to BERT and RoBERTa NLP models and tested against various NLP tasks using three adversarial NLP benchmarks and concluded that they could improve both the generalization and robustness of BERT and RoBERTa models.

Yoo et al. [57] argued that in NLP the generation of adversarial examples is a combinatorial optimization problem, which

¹⁵A deep learning approach proposed by Google

¹⁶<https://www.kaggle.com/francoisxa/ds2ostraffictaces>

is solved by deploying a heuristic algorithm. To this end, the authors proposed two methods to generate adversarial examples and improve the adversarial training process: (i) a cheaper gradient-based word importance ranking to sequentially replace each word with a synonym (A2T) and (ii) a masked language model-based word replacement (A2T-MLM). The proposed methods tested both BERT and RoBERTa NLP models on text classification tasks using well-known datasets (e.g., IMDB, Rotten Tomatoes, and SNLI). The experimental results showed that the A2T method could improve the NLP model’s robustness against several attacks of the literature (e.g., [58, 59, 60, 61]) that target NLP models.

Pan et al. [62] proposed an adversarial training method for text classification models. The authors based their method on white-box adversary’s knowledge. The adversarial sample generation process was based on FGSM and [51], but instead of applying the perturbations to the word embeddings, they applied them to the word embedding matrix of Transformer encoders. The experiments were performed using the BERT and RoBERTa NLP models on three datasets and compared on several tasks with other adversarial learning methods (e.g., PGD, FreeAT, FreeLB) [54]. The results showed that the proposed method outperforms PGD and FreeAT, while accomplishing the same performance as FreeLB.

Kitada et al. [52] introduced an adversarial training method that can be applied to various NLP tasks. The proposed adversarial training method is focused on the attention mechanism. More specifically, the generated adversarial perturbations are added to the attention mechanism to increase the model’s prediction performance and robustness. To test their method, the authors deployed a Bidirectional RNN (BiRNN) model and three different NLP tasks, text classification, question answering (QA), and natural language inference (NLi). The evaluation experiments concluded that the proposed adversarial training on the attention mechanism managed to improve the model’s performance on the three NLP tasks and outperformed other training techniques.

Finally, Morandi and Samwald [63] performed a large-scale investigation of the robustness of the biomedical NLP models against AML attacks. The authors performed white-box and black-box attack scenarios on both character-level and word-level AML attacks. More specifically, five biomedical/clinical textual datasets were used and four different NLP models were deployed based on BERT. Moreover, four AML attacks were performed and the results indicated that the NLP models are not robust to AML attacks. The authors employed adversarial training using adversarial examples generated by all the tested attacks and evaluated the performance of the models against adversarial and clean test samples to measure the robustness and generalization, respectively. The proposed approach tested several NLP tasks, such as question answering, semantic similarity estimation, natural language inference, text classification, and relation classification. The experimental results demonstrated that adversarial training improves the robustness and the generalization ability of biomedical NLP models.

AUDIO

In the audio domain, adversarial training has not received much attention, since it has been employed only in a few existing works.

Pal et al. [64] proposed a hybrid adversarial training method to improve the robustness of speaker recognition systems. For this purpose, the authors provide diverse and robust adversarial perturbations for adversarial training as a defense for deep speaker recognition systems against various types of attacks. Experiments were conducted on various white-box and black-box attacks, such as the FGSM, the C&W, the PGD, and the Feature Scattering attack (FS) [65]. The proposed hybrid adversarial training approach outperformed other adversarial training methods (e.g., using only FGSM, PGD, or FS adversarial examples) on all the testing AML attacks as well as on the detection of original examples.

Other defense methods against audio AML attacks relied on adversarial training in audio signals using a denoiser model [66]. The proposed defense is based on the adversarial training proposed in [37]. However, instead of adversarially training a model from scratch that leads to convergence issues in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR), the authors present a method to fine-tune a pre-trained ASR model using PGD adversarial examples. Then, the denoiser, which is pre-trained using deep regression, maps adversarial signals to benign ones. Experiments have been conducted using the FGSM and the PGD methods and demonstrated promising results. Nevertheless, more extensive tests still have to be conducted.

4.1.2. Defensive Distillation

The term distillation originally refers to the training procedure where a DNN model (student) is trained using knowledge transferred from a different DNN (teacher) [67]. The motivation for the use of distillation stems from the deployment of DL models in smaller devices (e.g., smartphones) that do not have the resources to perform complex computations, hence via distillation during the training phase, the knowledge is transferred from more complex DNN models.

Papernot et al. [68] employed an alternative to the distillation method to protect DNN against adversarial examples in the computer vision domain. They proposed the *defensive distillation* where instead of transferring knowledge between different DNN models, they extracted knowledge from a DNN to enhance its robustness against adversarial examples. The authors deployed the JSMA method to craft adversarial examples and two datasets (MNIST and CIFAR-10) to evaluate the defensive distillation. The defensive distillation method reduced the success rate of the adversarial examples from 95.89% to 0.45% on the MNIST dataset and from 87.89% to 5.11% on the CIFAR-10 dataset. Another work that studies the distillation method in AML domain is proposed in [69]. The authors presented the Adversarially Robust Distillation (ARD) method that combines distillation with adversarial training to transfer knowledge from robust teacher against AML attacks DNN models to student models. The experiments were performed using the adversarial training method proposed in [37] to train DNN models both with and without the ARD method on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 datasets. The evaluation concluded that the ARD-trained

models outperform the adversarially trained models.

Soll et al. [70] applied the defensive distillation method of the image classification domain to text classification. Particularly, the authors generated the text adversarial examples based on [71] and deployed two datasets (AG’s corpus of news articles and Amazon movie reviews) to test the defensive distillation on a CNN model. The experimental results indicated that the defensive distillation method did not have the same effect in the text classification domain as in image classification since the robustness of the CNN against the adversarial examples slightly increased.

Apruzzese et al. [72] proposed a defensive distillation approach for enhancing the robustness of RF in the cybersecurity domain (botnet network traffic detection). More specifically, the authors employed two RF models, one model to generate probability labels, namely they used the result of each Decision Tree (DT) of the RF ensemble algorithm to generate the probability for each sample to be malicious or benign, and then a second model was trained based on these probabilities. The proposed method evaluated adversarial examples only in the testing phase (i.e., the authors performed an evasion attack) generated by altering specific features of the dataset. The results concluded that it outperformed an undistilled model on both adversarial and non-adversarial examples. Moreover, the authors compared their method with other defense methods against AML attacks (e.g., adversarial training and feature reduction) and concluded that the proposed *defensive distillation* provides more resilience to RF against AML attacks.

Sidi et al. [73] presented MaskDGA, an evasion technique that is based on adversarial learning to alter Algorithmically Generated Domain (AGD) names to evade Domain Generation Algorithm (DGA) DL classifiers having knowledge only about the dataset that deployed to train the classifier (i.e., gray-box). The authors also employed the defensive distillation and adversarial training defenses to enhance the classifiers and test their performance against MaskDGA. The results regarding the deployed defenses concluded that distillation is an unreliable defense since it either improved or degraded the detection of adversarial samples, while adversarial training improved the accuracy of the classifiers against the specific attack in which they were trained; however, it did not generalize on other evasion attacks.

4.1.3. Ensemble Methods

The *Ensemble Methods* category is based on the concept of Ensemble Learning, namely multiple ML algorithms are combined to solve a learning problem (e.g., classification) [74]. Existing works in this category employ Ensemble Learning to enhance the resilience of ML and DL models against AML attacks.

Apruzzese et al. [75] proposed an approach named AppCon to enhance the resilience of ML (DT, RF, and AB) and DL (MLP and WnD) network IDS. AppCon is based on the paradigm of Ensemble Learning, namely, it employs an ensemble of detectors, where each detector is devoted to a particular web application (e.g., Skype, WhatsApp, etc.), and the results of the detectors are used to train and test a hardened detector.

The authors performed a gray-box adversarial attack adding small perturbations on specific features of the original botnet detection dataset (CTU-13). The experimental results indicated that AppCon could prevent the 75% of adversarial examples without affecting the performance in non-adversarial settings.

Jiang et al. [76] proposed a framework, named FGMD, which can effectively detect malicious IoT network traffic while it is also robust against AML evasion attacks. The authors proposed an adversarial sample generation approach that considers the constraints that arise due to the inherent properties of the network traffic (e.g., it cannot modify all the features of the network traffic, the attack function of the original malicious samples must be preserved, etc.). To this end, the authors altered only four features (from 23) to generate the adversarial examples and perform an evasion attack with black-box adversary knowledge. The FGMD framework is based on feature grouping and ensemble learning (referred to as model fusion). More specifically, the authors grouped the features into three categories and parsed them by three different LSTM models to perform the detection. The final prediction of the FGMD is calculated based on the average of the classification of the three models. The evaluation experiments were performed on two IoT datasets (MedBloT and IoTID) and FGMD compared with baseline models (LSTM, RNN, DT), both original and adversarially trained. The results indicate that FGMD can achieve higher scores (accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, FPR) than other models in the presence of AML evasion attack.

Ensemble methods are also used for the detection of adversarial audio samples. In [77], the authors investigate the impact of Gaussian smoothing on the DeepSpeech and Lingvo ASRs. Specifically, the authors present four defense systems, namely randomized smoothing, Defense GAN (uses the same technique as with images [78]), Variational autoencoder (VAE), and Parallel WaveGAN vocoder (PWG). The systems were compared with the standard defense systems for adversarial training. As an outcome, the authors propose a hybrid system where PWG is combined with randomized smoothing to provide 93% accuracy and 90% detection improvement for C&W and BIM attacks, which impose the greatest highest risk against audio systems.

4.1.4. Pre-processing

The *Pre-processing* category is comprised of existing works that utilize a pre-processing technique (e.g., feature reduction) to improve the model’s robustness against AML attacks.

Rosenberg et al. [79] proposed an attack-agnostic defense method for RNN classifiers against AML attacks that are named *Sequence Squeezing* based on an existing work proposed in [80]. However, it does not detect adversarial examples. Instead, this method merges semantically similar features (i.e., API call sequences) into a single representative feature. The evaluation experiments were performed on a dataset that includes API calls of benign and malware activity. The Sequence Squeezing method was also compared with other defense methods (e.g., adversarial training, adversarial signatures, RNN ensemble, Nearest Neighbor, defense sequence GAN) in four AML attacks (black-box gradient-based, white-box gradient-based, adaptive white-box attacker, and random perturbation). The

experimental results concluded that sequence squeezing is the only method that balances low overhead and high robustness.

Demontis et al. [81] delved into the evasion of AML attacks by investigating the concept of bounding classifier sensitivity to feature changes to improve the classifier’s security. The idea is to employ evenly-distributed feature weights to make the adversary alter more features to evade detection. The experiments were performed on an SVM classifier trained to detect Android malware. The authors concluded that the proposed approach enhances the classifier’s security by about ten times when considering the number of modifications required to create a malware sample that evades detection.

Esmailpour et al. [82] proposed an environmentally sound classification approach that is robust against AML attacks without incorporating any defense method (reactive or proactive). The SVM classifier was deployed since the authors argued that due to the fact that learns for low-dimensional feature vectors is less sensitive to adversarial perturbations compared to DNN. Before extracting the robust features, the authors employed a pre-processing approach named spectrogram pre-processing that aimed to enhance the resilience of the SVM model against AML attacks. Moreover, the authors focused on the feature extraction process by evaluating several handcrafted features to conclude on the Speed Up Robust Features (SURF). Several experiments were carried out to assess the performance of the proposed classification approach in both original and adversarial examples (in black-box adversary knowledge). The authors concluded that CNN models could accomplish comparable performance in audio classification tasks, but they can be easily fooled by adversarial examples achieving more than 94% fooling rate, while the proposed approach reduced the fooling rate to 50%.

Han et al. [83] proposed a defense method based on *feature reduction* to protect an ML-based malicious network traffic detector against the gray and black-box AML attacks. The authors calculated the adversarial robustness scores of the features and reduced the feature set by deleting the features with the lowest adversarial robustness scores. A thorough evaluation was performed, where six ML/DL algorithms (two of them were unsupervised) were deployed, namely Logistic Regression (LR), MLP, DT, SVM, Deep Autoencoders (DAE), and Isolation Forest (IF). Furthermore, the proposed defense method was compared with adversarial training and feature selection defenses, and the results indicate that feature reduction is more effective in accomplishing better results in reducing the malicious Traffic Evasion Rate (MER), Probability Decline Rate (PDR), Malicious features Mimicry Rate (MMR). However, the authors did not evaluate whether the proposed defense affects the performance of the original samples.

Weerasinghe et al. [84] introduced a defense method for SVM classifiers to tackle poisoning and label flipping attacks based on Local Intrinsic Dimensionality (LID) (i.e., a measurement to characterize the outlierness of data samples). The authors proposed the K-LID estimation to distinguish the adversarial and original samples based on their traits, which was deployed to enhance the resistance of an SVM classifier against training data manipulations. Several experiments were performed on various real-world datasets (e.g., image, audio classifica-

tion) to assess the performance of the K-LID SVM (i.e., testing against five different label-flipping attacks and one poisoning attack). The experiments concluded that the proposed defense could reduce the classification error rates by 10% on average.

Chen et al. [85] introduced a detection system for Android malware, named KuafuDet that contains an adversarial detection mechanism (camouflage) to protect the system against poisoning attacks. The camouflage detection deploys similarity-based filtering analysis to detect malicious data distortions. KuafuDet were tested against three threat models (weak attacker, strong attacker, and sophisticated attacker) that differ in the way they generate the adversarial examples. The experimental results concluded that KuafuDet enhances the detection accuracy by at least 15%, reducing the false negatives.

Liao et al. [86] introduced the concept of denoising adversarial examples as a defense against adversarial attacks that target ANN models in image classification tasks. The key innovation of the proposed method, name High-level representation Guided Denoiser (HGD) is that instead of using a pixel-level reconstruction loss function, they employed a loss function that considers the variations between top-level outputs of the target model activated by original and adversarial examples. The authors compared HGD with state-of-the-art ensemble adversarial training in both white-box and black-box attacks. Finally, they concluded that the proposed method accomplished higher accuracy while it requires less training data and training time.

Jia et al. [87] presented a defense method against black-box membership inference attacks, named MemGuard that leverages adversarial examples. In membership inference attacks the attacker deploys a binary classifier that takes input from the data sample’s confidence score vector predicted by the target classifier and predicts whether the data sample is a member of the training dataset of the target classifier. MemGuard adds noise to the confidence score vector, which is predicted by the target classifier converting it to an adversarial example that misleads the attacker’s classifier. The authors evaluated their approach in various experiments in the image classification field and showed that MemGuard and in consequence, adversarial examples can be an effective defense against membership inference attacks.

Zhang et al. [88] investigated the efficacy of feature selection as a defense against adversarial evasion attacks. To this end, the authors proposed a wrapper-based adversarial feature selection approach based on forward selection and backward elimination methods that not only improves the generalization capabilities of the classifier but also it optimizes its performance against black-box evasion attacks. The experiments were performed on two different use cases (e.g., spam and pdf malware detection) using a linear SVM classifier and concluded that can enhance the classifier’s security without significantly affecting its performance on normal settings (i.e., without the evasion attack).

Apruzzese et al. [89] proposed a set of gray-box attacks on phishing detectors and presented the concept of Protective Operation Chain (POC) as an effective mitigation technique against such attacks. The authors proposed four different gray-box attacks that were divided into simple and complex attacks

based on the features that an attacker alters. The POC method is basically an obfuscation method that is based on the generation of a new feature space by randomly mixing a portion of the features that the phishing detector employs in order to make it harder for the attacker to comprehend which features are deployed by the detector and how these features indicate the phishing or benign websites. A comprehensive evaluation of the proposed defense solution was performed using four different phishing datasets and 13 ML classifiers. The authors concluded that POC is robust to all 13 classifiers. Moreover, to demonstrate the significance of POC against existing baselines, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was employed along with the Bonferroni correction and showed that POC improves the robustness of the existing baselines at the $p < 0.001$ level.

4.2. Detection

In contrast to the *Mitigation* category, the *Detection* category focuses on reactive defenses whose purpose is to detect AML attacks (e.g., detection of adversarial examples) before they reach the ML/DL models.

4.2.1. Supervised/Semi-supervised Learning

The category *Supervised/Semi-supervised Learning* includes methods that detect AML deploying an auxiliary ML/DL model that has been trained using supervised or semi-supervised learning.

Pawlick et al. [90] developed a detection method for AML attacks against ANN-NIDS. The authors specifically utilized four well-known adversarial attacks (C&W, FGSM, BIM, and PGD) to generate adversarial examples. The original samples (both malicious and benign) are labeled as “non-adversarial” based on the activation of each neuron of the ANN-IDS. The generated adversarial examples, along with the “non-adversarial”, deployed to form a new adversarial dataset that contains the labels *adversarial* and *non-adversarial*. Moreover, the authors deployed five ML algorithms (ANN, RF, KNN, SVM, AB) to detect whether a sample is related to an AML attack and evaluated them on the CIC-IDS dataset. The best results were accomplished with RF and k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithms that attained 99% recall for AML attacks.

Taheri et al. [91] presented a label-flipping attack (Silhouette-based Label Flipping) along with two defense methods (label-based semi-supervised and clustering-based semi-supervised defense) that applied on a CNN classifier. The authors deployed their approach on the Android malware detection field using three different datasets (i.e., Drebin, Contagio, and Genome). The experimental results concluded that using clustering-based semi-supervised along with RF feature selection, the accuracy improved by 19% in comparison with state-of-the-art defenses.

The authors of [92] proposed a detection method, named PDGAN, to defend poisoning attacks against Federated Learning models. The attacker’s goal is to compromise the global model by uploading malicious updates from the poisoned local model. This is achieved by performing a label-flipping attack on the training dataset of the local model and computing the poisoned local updates. The PDGAN detection method implements a GAN on the server to reconstruct the training data.

Then, the training data are fed to each participant model to get the labels of each sample and calculate the accuracy of the participants’ models. First, the participant’s models were classified as benign and attackers (based on a threshold value), and later the PDGAN considers only the updates that the benign participants have performed. The authors evaluate the PDGAN on the image classification field using two datasets (MNIST and Fashion-MNIST). The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method can immediately reduce the poisoning accuracy from almost 90% to 3.1% and accomplish an overall accuracy of almost 90%.

Recent defenses in the audio domain are based on randomization schemes to mitigate the effects of AML attacks on the audio samples. The authors in [93] use a randomization technique based on recursive filters. The technique first transforms the audio waveform into the frequency domain, resulting in a signal spectrogram. In parallel, recursive filters that are incorporating randomness are applied in the original audio to produce a new spectrogram that is different from the original. Randomness is considered in the form of probabilistic distributions. Both spectrograms are fed into an ASR system which compares them and derives their transcribed sentences using the word error rate. In the same manner, the ASR system can detect changes if the original audio is malformed due to an AML attack. This ASR system technique provides protection against both high-frequency and low-frequency audio signals and is resilient to adaptive attacks. The evaluation is performed in the C&W and PsyImp [94] AML attacks using DeepSpeech as well as Lingvo ASR systems and demonstrates a good detection performance for different probabilistic distributions (e.g., Gamma, Uniform, Normal).

Lin et al. [95] treat the defense as a functional high-order function that parses each adversarial sample and returns a new defender function for each particular sample. The proposed defense approach deploys an iterative self-supervised learning model based on Denoising Autoencoder to identify the original (unattacked) data for each adversarial sample to recover the prediction. This defense works in white-box and gray-box adversarial settings and was tested on image classification tasks using a strong white-box attack (i.e., BPDA), accomplishing 98%, 76%, and 43% accuracy on MNIST, CIFAR-10, and ImageNet datasets respectively.

In [96], the authors investigated the performance of self-supervised learning models against black-box AML attacks in ASR tasks. During the training phase, these models are also learning a mapping function that maps the input to high-level representations. This work showed that self-supervised learning models can be used as filters that extract pivotal information from the contaminated input spectrograms to tackle AML attacks. The experiments conducted using DL anti-spoofing models and well-known AML attacks (e.g., FGSM and PGD) concluded that the proposed defense is very effective regardless of the amount of attack signal.

Tuinen et al. [97] proposed two methods for the detection of adversarial examples that target image classifiers using white-box adversary’s knowledge. The first method employs a CNN model that is trained to detect adversarial examples that have

been generated by a distribution, while the second method down-samples the images to a lower dimension using the Discrete Cosine Transform method and performs the detection using an SVM classifier. The experiments performed on PGD white-box attacks and concluded that both methods can attain high prediction accuracy with some trade-off in efficiency.

4.2.2. Distance-based

In the *Distance-based* category, the detection of AML attacks is performed by measuring the distance between adversarial and original samples.

Paudice et al. [98] proposed an outlier detection method for poisoning attacks. Particularly, the authors deployed a distance-based anomaly detection for the detection of adversarial training samples using a part of original (i.e., trusted) data samples. The evaluation was performed on two benchmark datasets in spam filtering and computer vision domains as well as on KNN and SVM ML algorithms. The results concluded that the proposed method is capable of mitigating poisoning attacks. Furthermore, the authors evaluated their detection method for label-flipping attacks; however, the results were not encouraging because the generated adversarial examples were closer to the original, and the proposed detection method failed to detect them effectively.

Meng et al. [99] presented a framework, named MagNet, for defending ANNs image classifiers against AML attacks that are independent of the target classifier and the deployed adversarial examples generation process (i.e., it is attack-agnostic). MagNet consists of two components, the *detector* and the *reformer*. The detector rejects a sample that exceeds the boundary, while the reformer finds an alternative example closer to the boundary and sends that to the ANN classifier. More specifically, MagNet models only the original samples and estimates the distance of the test samples and the boundary of the manifold of the original samples. The authors used various AML attacks to generate the adversarial examples (e.g., C&W, FGSM, DeepFool, etc.) as well as the MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets. The results showed that MagNet significantly increased the accuracy against all the attacks, while the accuracy only on original samples was reduced by 3.8%.

Esmailpour et al. [100] proposed a detection method that explores subspaces of adversarial examples in the unitary vector domain and developed a detector based on LR to defend models on environmental sound classification field. Specifically, the authors calculated chordal distance eigenvalues of legitimate and adversarial examples, which were deployed to train the LR classifier. The experiments were performed on three datasets (ESC-10, ESC-50, and UrbanSound8k) using eight different types of AML attacks (e.g., FGSM, BIM, JSMA, label flipping, etc.). The results concluded that the proposed detector achieved high performance in detecting all the attacks as well as it outperformed other detectors (e.g., kernel density, Bayesian uncertainty, and local intrinsic dimensionality) in six out of eight adversarial attacks.

The authors in [101] introduced a distance-based method for the detection of adversarial inputs in audio samples. The

method is based on a recognition model, which performs classification to first characterize the original audio, and then it receives the modified audio as input. The modified audio is generated using low-pass filtering mechanisms, where the spectrum, waveform, and accuracy rate of the audio signal are analyzed. If the difference between the modified and the original audio is sufficiently large, then the original audio sample is regarded as an adversarial example. Similarly, if the difference is small, the original audio sample is regarded as a normal sample. The method is evaluated on the Mozilla Common Voice dataset¹⁷, where the C&W attack is performed to generate the adversarial audio samples and the results concluded that it outperforms other detection methods, such as white noise, denoise down-sampling, and temporal dependency. Another defense approach for adversarial audio detection is illustrated in [102], where distance-based techniques were followed to perform the detection. The authors introduced a novel ASR framework that performs similarity calculation through binary classification. The similarity is measured using the Jaro-Winkler distance method [103]. The method uses multiple ASRs to achieve a higher accuracy reaching even up to 99.88%.

Yang et al. [104] proposed a detection method against AML attacks for ASR models. The proposed method relied on the temporal dependency in speech signals. The audio sample is split into portions, and the defense framework evaluates the transcription of the portion against the original sample. The portion transcription is based on different transformation functions, such as quantization, down-sampling, local smoothing, and auto-encoder reformation of audio signals. The authors verified the portions that are not similar using the Word Error Rate (WER) and the Character Error Rate (CER). The results showed that the proposed temporal dependency detection method could effectively detect adversarial audio examples.

A similar approach that detects audio AML attacks in ASR models is the WaveGuard framework [105]. WaveGuard uses transformation functions and analyses the ASR transcriptions of the original and transformed audio. These functions are leveraging Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for the detection of AML attacks. WaveGuard is able to detect AML attacks with a variety of audio transformation functions.

Chen et. al [106] introduced a stateful method for detecting black-box AML attacks in image classification tasks. The authors based their work on the argument that the generation process of adversarial examples requires a sequence of similar queries to the classifier and developed a detection method deploying a neural network similarity-detector and proved that this approach can detect existing state-of-the-art black-box attack algorithms. Towards the same direction, Li et al. [107] introduced a detection-based defense method for query-based black-box AML attacks using a content-similarity approach, named Blacklight. Blacklight was driven by the fact that query-based black-box attacks result in highly similar queries and is comprised of two components: the *probabilistic content fingerprinting* that aims at fast and scalable attack detection, and

¹⁷<https://commonvoice.mozilla.org/>

the *salted pixel quantization* that aims at providing resistance against adaptive attacks. Blacklight was evaluated against various black-box attacks on several datasets and image classification models and showed that it can detect all the attacks after 2-9 queries (except boundary attack that takes 50 queries on average) and that it consistently reduces the attack success rate to 0% for all the tested attack. Finally, the authors showed that Blacklight can generalize also to other domains and employed a text-classification task as an example.

Song et al. [108] proposed three mutation-based evasion attacks that were evaluated under white-box, black-box, and gray-box attack settings on ML-based phishing website classifiers and are highly effective in accomplishing 100% success rate on Google’s phishing page filter (GPPF). The authors expand their research by introducing also two similarity-based detection mechanisms (i.e., DOM tree and personalized similarity) to tackle these attacks. The experimental results on large phishing and legitimate URL corpus concluded that both DOM tree and personalized similarity achieved over 90% similarity on most of the adversarial samples in white-box and black-box settings, while in gray-box settings personalized similarity significantly outperformed DOM tree.

4.2.3. Feature Squeezing

Xu et al. [80] introduced *Feature Squeezing*, a method to detect adversarial examples in the computer vision domain. The method is based on two-dimensionality reduction techniques: i) Color bit depth reduction (from 24-bit to 8-bit) and ii) spatial smoothing (i.e., blur). The first technique is based on the fact that the image’s colors are unrelated to the classification; hence they will not affect the model’s classification accuracy when reduced. Spatial smoothing, on the other hand, employs local smoothing and non-local smoothing to reduce the image’s noise. During the Feature Squeezing process, two versions of the input image are produced based on the two aforementioned techniques. A DNN classifies the original image and the two generated images, and their outputs are compared using the L_1 metric. If L_1 exceeds a threshold, the image is classified as adversarial and discarded.

4.2.4. Statistical

Grosse et al. [109] proposed a detection method based on *Statistical* tests for adversarial examples. Two statistical distance metrics (Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) and Energy Distance (ED)) were employed to measure the distance of adversarial and original samples, namely to identify their differences. The authors evaluated their method on four classifiers (ANN, DT, LR, SVM), three different domains, such as image classification (MNIST), malware detection (Drebin), and cancer detection (MicroRNA), as well as four AML attacks (FGSM, JSMA, SVM attack, and Decision Tree attack) and concluded that it could effectively detect the adversarial examples.

Table 4 summarizes all the above-mentioned defense methods based on key traits, such as year, deployed attack type (i.e., poisoning or evasion), attacker’s knowledge (i.e., black/white/gray-box), application domain, evaluated ML/DL algorithms, as well

as the employed defense method (e.g., adversarial training, ensemble methods, pre-processing, etc.).

5. Evaluation of Defense Methods

This section aims to provide insights regarding the efficient evaluation of defenses (both mitigation and detection methods) against AML attacks. However, in order to accurately evaluate the defense methods and avoid misleading results, it should be assured that the attack has been implemented correctly. Several works in the literature highlight that existing defenses fail to perform successful attacks resulting in misleading results and suggest guidelines that aim to lead to unbiased results. Carlini et al. [110] performed a large-scale analysis of commonly accepted best practices discussing their limitations and introduced new methods for accurately evaluating defenses against adversarial examples. Moreover, Pintor et al. [111] proposed a framework to automatically detect erroneous evaluations of adversarial robustness that researchers could employ to build robust defenses. In the rest of this section, datasets from the literature that contain both original and adversarial samples (hereafter *AML datasets*) have been gathered and presented. In addition, *evaluation metrics* that have been specifically created to assess the robustness of AI systems or defense methods against AML attacks have been collected and discussed. Finally, the importance of evaluating the economic viability when proposing a new defense has been highlighted. It should be noted that common evaluation metrics such as *accuracy*, *precision*, *recall*, and *F1-score* are not considered in this section since they are not appropriate for measuring the robustness of AI systems in adversarial settings [112].

5.1. Dataset gathering

In this section, we gathered the AML datasets that have been introduced by existing works and are publicly available to evaluate ML/DL models’ robustness. To the best of our knowledge, only seven AML datasets are publicly available, six of them belong to the computer vision domain and one to the sound classification. These datasets are presented below:

1. DAmageNet [113] is an AML dataset that provides black-box AML attack images. It contains 96,020 adversarial samples generated from the original samples of the ImageNet dataset. DAmageNet is appropriate for testing and improving the robustness of DNN in image classification tasks¹⁸.
2. In [114] four variations of the CIFAR dataset have been proposed in order for the authors to demonstrate that adversarial samples are a result of non-robust features (i.e., features that can be easily predicted but are incomprehensible to humans). The datasets are publicly available¹⁹ and contain both robust and non-robust features (i.e., both original and adversarial samples) appropriate for image classification tasks.

¹⁸<http://www.pami.sjtu.edu.cn/Show/56/122>

¹⁹<https://github.com/MadryLab/constructed-datasets>

Table 4: Summary of AML Defense Methods

Paper	Year	Attack Type	Attacker's Knowledge	Domain	Algorithm	Defense Method
Anthi et al. [25]	2021	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-ICS	RF/J48	Adversarial Training
Vitorino et al. [50]	2022	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-IoT	MLP/RF	Adversarial Training
Khamis et al. [29]	2020	Evasion	White-box	Cybersecurity-Network	DNN/RF/AB/NB/SVM	Adversarial Training
Khamis et al. [46]	2020	Evasion	White-box	Cybersecurity-Network	CNN/RNN	Adversarial Training
Apuzzese et al. [49]	2020	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-Botnet	RF/WnD	Adversarial Training
Fu et al. [47]	2021	Evasion	White-box	Cybersecurity-Network	CNN/LSTM/GRU	Adversarial Training
Rashid et al. [34]	2022	Evasion	N/A	Cybersecurity-IoT	MLP/DT/RF	Adversarial Training
Goodfellow et al. [28]	2014	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Huang et al. [36]	2015	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Madry et al. [37]	2017	Evasion	Black/White-box	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Sankaranarayanan et al. [38]	2018	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Shafahi et al. [39]	2019	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Xie et al. [40]	2019	Evasion	Black/White-box	Image Classification	CNN	Adversarial Training
Tramèr et al. [41]	2017	Evasion	Black/White-box	Image Classification	CNN/FCN	Adversarial Training
Lal et al. [42]	2021	Evasion	Black/White-box	Image Classification	CNN	Adversarial Training & Feature Reduction
Ding et al. [43]	2021	Evasion	N/A	Visual Context Prediction	cGAN	Adversarial Training
Xu et al. [44]	2021	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Adversarial Training
Liu et al. [56]	2020	Evasion	N/A	NLP	BERT/RoBERTa	Adversarial Training
Yoo et al. [57]	2021	Evasion	N/A	Text Classification	BERT/RoBERTa	Adversarial Training
Pan et al. [62]	2021	Evasion	White-box	Text Classification	BERT/RoBERTa	Adversarial Training
Kitada et al. [52]	2021	Evasion	N/A	NLP	RNN	Adversarial Training
Morandi et al. [63]	2022	Evasion	Black/White-box	NLP	BERT	Adversarial Training
Pal et al. [64]	2021	Evasion	Black/White-box	Speech Recognition	DNN	Adversarial Training
Sonal et al. [66]	2022	Evasion	White-box	Speech Recognition	CNN	Adversarial Training
Papernot et al. [68]	2016	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Defensive Distillation
Goldblum [69]	2020	Evasion	N/A	Image Classification	DNN	Defensive Distillation
Soll et al. [70]	2019	Evasion	N/A	Text Classification	CNN	Defensive Distillation
Apuzzese et al. [72]	2020	Evasion	N/A	Cybersecurity-Botnet	RF	Defensive Distillation
Sidi et al. [73]	2020	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-Botnet	CNN/LSTM	Defensive Distillation
Apuzzese et al. [75]	2020	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-Botnet	DT/RF/MLP/AB/WnD	Ensemble Methods
Jiang et al. [76]	2022	Evasion	Black-box	Cybersecurity-IoT	LSTM	Ensemble Methods
Sonal et al. [77]	2021	Evasion	White-box	Speech Recognition	DNN	Ensemble Methods
Rosenberg et al. [79]	2019	Evasion	Black/White-box	Cybersecurity-Network	RNN	Pre-processing
Xu et al. [80]	2017	Evasion	White-box	Audio Classification	DNN	Feature Squeezing
Demontis et al. [81]	2017	Evasion	N/A	Cybersecurity-Android	SVM	Pre-processing
Esmailpour et al. [82]	2019	Evasion	Black-box	Audio Classification	SVM	Pre-processing
Han et al. [83]	2021	Evasion	Gray/Black-box	Cybersecurity-Network	LR/MLP/DT/SVM/DAE/IF	Pre-processing
Weerasinghe et al. [84]	2021	Poisoning	Gray-box	Image & Audio Classification	SVM	Pre-processing
Chen et al. [85]	2018	Poisoning	Gray-box	Cybersecurity	SVM	Pre-processing
Liao et al. [86]	2018	Poisoning	Black/White-box	Image Classification	CNN	Pre-processing
Jia et al. [87]	2018	Poisoning	Black-box	Image Classification	FCNN	Pre-processing
Zhang et al. [88]	2015	Evasion	Black-box	Cybersecurity-Malware/Spam	SVM	Pre-processing
Apuzzese et al. [89]	2022	Evasion	Gray-box	Cybersecurity-Phishing	RF/MLP/NB/KNN/DT/SVM	Pre-processing
Pawlick et al. [90]	2020	Evasion	White-box	Cybersecurity-Network	ANN/RF/KNN/SVM/AB	Supervised Learning
Tao et al. [93]	2021	Evasion	N/A	Speech Recognition	DNN	Supervised Learning
Taheri et al. [91]	2020	Poisoning	Black-box	Cybersecurity-Android	CNN	Semi-supervised Learning
Zhao et al. [92]	2019	Poisoning	White-box	Image Classification	Federated Learning	GAN
Lin et al. [95]	2019	Evasion	White/Gray-box	Image Classification	CNN	Self-supervised learning
Wu et al. [96]	2020	Evasion	White/Gray-box	Speech Recognition	CNN	Self-supervised learning
Tuinen et al. [97]	2022	Evasion	White-box	Image Classification	CNN	Semi-supervised learning
Paudice et al. [98]	2018	Poisoning	N/A	Spam Filtering & Computer Vision	KNN/SVM	Distance-based Detection
Meng et al. [99]	2017	Evasion	Black-box	Image Classification	ANN	Distance-based Detection
Esmailpour et al. [100]	2020	Poisoning & Evasion	N/A	Audio Classification	CNN/SVM	Distance-based Detection
Kwon et al. [101]	2020	Evasion	Gray-box	Audio Classification	DNN	Distance-based Detection
Zeng et al. [102]	2019	Evasion	White/Black-box	Speech Recognition	DNN	Distance-based Detection
Yang et al. [104]	2018	Evasion	N/A	Speech Recognition	DNN	Distance-based Detection
Hussain et al. [105]	2021	Evasion	White-box	Speech Recognition	DNN	Distance-based Detection
Chen et al. [106]	2020	Evasion	Black-box	Image Classification	DNN	Distance-based Detection
Li et al. [107]	2022	Evasion	Black-box	Image & Text Classification	CNN/DNN	Distance-based Detection
Song et al. [108]	2021	Evasion	Black/Gray/White-box	Cybersecurity-Phishing	GPPF	Distance-based Detection
Grosse et al. [109]	2017	Poisoning & Evasion	Black/White-box	Image & Malware & Cancer Classification	ANN/DT/LR/SVM	Statistical

- The authors of [39] generated two AML datasets based on the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 using PGD AML attack to produce the adversarial examples²⁰. These datasets can be deployed to develop robust image classification models or evaluate the models' robustness against PGD attacks.
- The APRICOT dataset [115] was developed to deceive object detectors. It is comprised of 1000 images of printed adversarial patches photographed in real-world scenes (i.e., public locations)²¹. The samples are generated to represent various viewing angles, positions, light, and distance conditions. Furthermore, this dataset can be used to assess the robustness of object detectors as well as to

facilitate researchers in developing methods for flagging adversarial patches.

- The authors of [116] introduced two adversarial datasets based on ImageNet, named ImageNet-A and ImageNet-O²². ImageNet-A is comprised of real-world adversarially filtered images that can be employed to assess image classifiers' robustness, while ImageNet-O contains adversarially filtered images to evaluate out-of-distribution detection models.
- In [117], the authors proposed a simulation tool for generating synthetic datasets with realistic adversarial samples using the CARLA simulator²³. This dataset can be deployed to test the adversarial robustness of frameworks

²⁰https://github.com/ashafahi/free_adv_train/tree/master/datasets

²¹<https://apricot.mitre.org/download/>

²²<https://github.com/hendrycks/natural-adv-examples>

²³<https://carla.org/>

in object detection tasks and similar research fields such as autonomous driving.

7. Adv-ESC (Adversarial Environmental Sound Classification) dataset [26] is the first environmental sound dataset equipped with adversarial examples, which can serve as a benchmark evaluation dataset to train robust sound classification models. Adv-ESC is based on two environmental sound classification datasets (ESC-10 and DCASE task 1A) and is comprised of adversarial examples generated by FGSM, PGD, and BIM methods.

It has been observed that only a few AML datasets are publicly available, where the vast majority can only be applied to the computer vision domain and, more specifically, to image classification and object detection tasks. There is a clear need for more AML datasets that can also be applied to other domains, such as cybersecurity, where AML attacks are on the rise. Hence, future research on AML should also consider the introduction of benchmark AML datasets in various domains to facilitate researchers evaluating their defense methods and comparing them with existing works on common ground.

5.2. Evaluation Metrics

This section elaborates on metrics that existing works utilized to measure the efficacy of their defense solutions against AML attacks. Most works employ common metrics to evaluate the robustness against AML attacks (e.g., accuracy, F1-score, AUC); however, a few introduce new metrics. Accordingly, these metrics are discussed.

Malicious traffic Evasion Rate (MER) [83]. It measures how much original malicious network traffic can be evasive. MER is the percentage of undetected mutated malicious traffic to originally detectable traffic.

$$MER = 1 - \frac{P_{UMTmal}}{P_{DT}} \quad (5)$$

Detection Evasion Rate (DER) [83]. This metric is similar to MER but measures how much of the mutated traffic can be evasive. DER also measures whether the adversarially generated traffic is detected as malicious. DER is the percentage of undetected mutated traffic to originally detectable traffic.

$$DER = 1 - \frac{P_{UMT}}{P_{DT}} \quad (6)$$

Malicious Probability Decline Rate (PDR) [83]. PDR measures the decline rate of the malicious probabilities produced by the classifier.

$$PDR = 1 - E_{(f, \hat{f}) \in (F_{mal}, \hat{F}_{mal})} \frac{C(\hat{f})}{C(f)} \quad (7)$$

Malicious features Mimicry Rate (MMR) [83]. This metric measures the extent to which adversarial crafted features are close to malicious features extracted from mutated traffic.

$$MMR = 1 - E_{(f, \hat{f}, f_a) \in (F_{mal}, \hat{F}_{mal}, F_{adv})} \frac{L(\hat{f}, f_a)}{L(f, f_a)} \quad (8)$$

Fooling Rate (FR) [82]. This metric is based on the error rate and computes the ratio of successful fooling adversarial samples (SAS) over the total number of adversarial samples (TAS).

$$FR = \frac{SAS_{im}}{TAS_i^T} \quad (9)$$

Attack Success Rate (ASR) [118]. The ratio of misclassified adversarial samples (MAS) to the total number of adversarial samples (TAS).

$$ASR = \frac{MAS_{im}}{TAS_i^T} \quad (10)$$

Attack Severity (AS) [75]. AS measures the efficacy of an evasion AML attack considering the detection rate (DR) before and after the attack.

$$AS = 1 - \frac{DR_{after}}{DR_{before}} \quad (11)$$

6. Discussion

Even though AML has received significant attention in the last five years and new AML attacks are constantly introduced or existing attacks are applied to different fields, the defense methods against AML attacks are still in their infancy. Based on the surveyed articles limited research is available regarding mitigating or detecting AML attacks. Table 5 provides a comparison of the existing defenses in the AML field based on numerous criteria, such as whether the defense method is attack-agnostic (i.e., can mitigate/detect multiple AML attacks) or domain-agnostic (i.e., it has been tested on several domains), whether it was evaluated using AML evaluation metrics (discussed in section 5.2), the application domain, the defense method category (i.e., mitigation or detection), and the evaluated models (i.e., ML or DL). Moreover, Table 5 (Code and Dataset columns) presents which of the surveyed existing works publicly release the source code and the dataset. It should be clearly mentioned that the dataset criterion refers to the deployed AML dataset. For instance, the authors of [50] utilized a publicly available dataset to generate an AML dataset; however, they did not share the generated dataset.

As can be observed by Table 5, most existing defense methods focus on improving the resiliency of ML/DL models (i.e., on the mitigation category) against AML attacks rather than detecting them. More specifically, approximately 78% of the surveyed defenses deal with the mitigation of AML attacks. This can be attributed to the fact that adversarial training is one of the first defense methods that are still extremely popular because researchers strive to introduce adversarial training methods which do not affect the model's performance in non-adversarial settings. Furthermore, only 6.55% of the surveyed defenses are attack-agnostic, and almost 5% are domain-agnostic, indicating that most of the existing defenses cannot cope with multiple AML attacks neither can be applied to more

Table 5: Comparison of AML Defense Methods

Paper	Attack-agnostic	Domain-agnostic	AML Evaluation Metrics	Domain			Defense		Model		Publicly Available	
				Cybersecurity	Computer Vision	NLP	Audio	Mitigation	Detection	ML	DL	Code
Anthi et al. [25]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Vitorino [50]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Khamis et al. [29]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Khamis et al. [46]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Apruzzese et al. [49]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Fu et al. [47]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Rashid et al. [34]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Goodfellow et al. [28]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Huang et al. [36]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Madry et al. [37]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Sankaranarayanan et al. [38]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Shafahi et al. [39]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Xie et al. [40]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Tramèr et al. [41]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Lal et al. [42]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Ding et al. [43]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Xu et al. [44]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Liu et al. [56]	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Yoo et al. [57]	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Pan et al. [62]	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Kitada et al. [52]	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Moradi et al. [63]	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Papernot et al. [68]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Goldblum et al. [69]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Soll et al. [70]	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Apruzzese et al. [72]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Sidi et al. [73]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Apruzzese et al. [75]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Jiang et al. [76]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Rosenberg et al. [79]	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Demontis et al. [81]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Esmailpour et al. [82]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Han et al. [83]	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Weerasinghe et al. [84]	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Chen et al. [85]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Liao et al. [86]	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓
Jia et al. [87]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Zhang et al. [88]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Apruzzese et al. [89]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Pawlicki et al. [90]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Lin et al. [95]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Wu [96]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Tuinen et al. [97]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Paudice et al. [98]	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Meng et al. [99]	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Esmailpour et al. [100]	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Taheri et al. [91]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Zhao et al. [92]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x
Pal et al. [64]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Sonal et al. [66]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Sonal et al. [77]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Xu et al. [80]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Grosse et al. [109]	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Tao et al. [93]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Kwon et al. [101]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Zeng et al. [102]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Yang et al. [104]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Hussain et al. [105]	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
Chen et al. [106]	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Li et al. [107]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
Song et al. [108]	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x

than one domain. Most previous works were not validated using appropriate evaluation metrics since the works that have been evaluated using AML evaluation metrics are only 14.75% (the majority employs the ASR metric). Last but not least, limited information is publicly shared by the authors of existing works to facilitate the scientific community to reproduce their results and compare them with future works considering that only a few works share the code (36%) and only one its deployed dataset (3.27%).

Analyzing the results of the taxonomy per domain, it has been observed that in NLP and audio domains, the existing research is in its infancy since only a few defenses exist in these domains. However, an interesting observation is that in the speech recognition and audio classification fields, most works focus on evasion AML attacks deploying distance-based detection methods [104]. Regarding the Computer Vision domain,

the vast majority of existing defenses focused on the image classification field implementing mostly mitigation methods (i.e., adversarial training) to enhance the robustness of CNN [40] and DNN [37] models. The number of works in the detection category is significantly lower and these works employ self- and semi-supervised learning [95, 97] as well as distance-based detection [98, 99, 106]. Furthermore, regarding the cybersecurity domain, most of the existing research works focus on the mitigation category of the taxonomy and particularly show that the implementation of adversarial training can overall improve the models’ robustness in the evaluated areas (e.g., IoT attacks, botnets, and malicious network traffic detection) [25, 29, 34, 50, 119]. However, there are also a few works that studied the application of Ensemble Learning and proved that the combination of multiple ML/DL algorithms is more robust than using a single ML/DL algorithm in the bot-

net [89] and IoT attack detection fields [76]. Defensive distillation and feature pre-processing have been also investigated in [72] and [81] respectively to enhance the models' robustness against AML attacks in botnet and Android malware ML-based detectors. Moreover, limited attention has been given to the detection part of the taxonomy, where existing works employ supervised and semi-supervised learning methods to detect AML attacks [90, 91].

The taxonomy introduced in this work revealed several gaps and open problems in the existing literature that paved the way for identifying some directions for future research in the AML defense domain. ML/DL models are utilized almost in every technological domain. Consequently, the surface of AML attacks is massive; hence, it is crucial to develop domain-agnostic defenses (i.e., a defense that can be applied to several domains). From the surveyed defenses, only two works ([98] and [109]) evaluated their defenses on more than one domain. Thus, one direction for future research could focus on developing domain-agnostic defenses. Towards the same direction, AML attacks are evolving as new attacks are continuously emerging. Therefore, it is crucial to develop defense methods that are attack-agnostic. However, currently, only a few existing defense methods are attack-agnostic (e.g., [79], [99], [100], [109]). Hence, a second direction for future research is designing new attack-agnostic defenses. Moreover, since existing defenses mostly deal with mitigating AML attacks, there is a gap in defense methods that concentrate on detecting AML attacks. To this end, a possible third future research direction could focus on proposing innovative detection methods for AML attacks or hybrid solutions that will combine both mitigation and detection. Finally, several works in the literature (e.g., [120, 121]) highlight the fact that time performance is a significant parameter that should be examined during the evaluation of ML and DL models. However, existing literature in the field of AML defense usually omits to include this information. In addition, evaluating the robustness of ML/DL models is a critical issue, and proper evaluation metrics and datasets for AML attacks should be considered. Hence, a fourth research direction could emphasize considering time complexity in the evaluation of AML attacks and defense solutions as well as proposing new AML evaluation metrics and datasets.

Along with the AML attack and defense taxonomy introduced in this article, the attackers' motivations should be also studied in terms of economic viability aspects [14, 122]. This is performed in the form of a cost-benefit analysis to determine the potential gains of launching an AML cyber-attack against a specific target. Specifically, if a target has higher potential economic or reputation rewards or even is prone to multiple vulnerabilities that can be exploited, this target will be selected over an attack that requires significant effort and time with a lower potential reward. To cope with economic viability aspects, research efforts should focus on building a cost-based AML threat model [123]. This model will allow the computation of likelihood (based on AML threats as well as system vulnerabilities) and impact of AML cyber-attacks in the financial, reputational, legal, and regulatory domains. Then, it is able to prioritize the AML defense methods (both mitigation

and detection categories), which should be enabled to avoid the potential damages of AML threats in terms of organization resources, and assets. A well-known approach for conducting a prioritization is the use of risk assessment procedures based on the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Special Publication (SP) 800-30 standard [124]. This standard identifies risks in the form of a risk heatmap, where the highest priority risks are to be immediately procured for implementing AML defense methods. An example of such a heatmap is illustrated in Figure 5. The heatmap defines four individual categories: 1) *normal*, which indicates no risk, 2) *low*, which indicates minimal risk, 3) *medium*, which indicates that the risk is adequate, 4) *high*, which needs indicates a clear and severe threat to the system and 5) *critical*, which is the highest risk and needs to be treated immediately.

Figure 5: Risk Heatmap

7. Conclusion

AML attacks are constantly enhanced compromising the efficacy of AI systems. In the last couple of years, the research is focusing on the defenses against AML, introducing innovative methods that either delve into increasing the robustness of ML/DL models or detecting AML attacks. Even though numerous surveys exist in the literature that elaborates on novel AML attack methods, no surveys focus solely on the existing defenses against AML. To the best of our knowledge, this article introduced the first large-scale and domain-agnostic survey of AML defenses aiming to address the current knowledge gap and provide directions for future research. Particularly, a taxonomy of the existing works was introduced, where the defenses were grouped into two major categories *mitigation* and *detection*. The strengths and weaknesses of each work were discussed, providing a comprehensive view of the existing defenses and identifying limitations and gaps in the literature. Moreover, the article collected and presented novel metrics developed to evaluate the robustness of ML/DL models against AML attacks and the efficacy of detection systems focusing on detecting AML attacks as well as AML datasets ready to be deployed for the evaluation of defense methods. Finally, based on the gaps identified

by the proposed taxonomy, this article discussed the directions that future research should focus on to facilitate the scientific community proposing new defense solutions to tackle AML.

A final takeaway derived from our survey is that AML attack landscape grows exponentially and becomes increasingly sophisticated threatening AI systems regardless of their application domain, while on the other hand, the defense methods are inadequate to address this threat since existing methods mainly focusing on adversarial training. A key solution could be the investigation and application of AI methods designed to tackle cyber-attacks in the AML field (e.g., [125, 126, 127]). As a future direction, the creation of a holistic benchmark evaluation framework for AML defenses is envisaged. This framework will facilitate researchers upon assessing their solutions under the same settings reducing common evaluation problems, such as inappropriate evaluation metrics and limited information about datasets.

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